

One Step at a Time: Combining LLMs and Static Analysis to Generate Next-Step Hints for Programming Tasks

CONTENTS

1 In-IDE Learning	2
2 General Pipeline	3
2.1 Generating subgoals	3
2.2 Generating textual and code hints	3
3 Internal Validation	5
3.1 “Kotlin Onboarding: Introduction” course	5
3.2 Validating the generation of subgoals	6
3.3 Validating the generation of hints	7

1 IN-IDE LEARNING

Figure 1.1 demonstrates an example of how the user interface of the JetBrains Academy plugin [1] looks for a student. The interface consists of five main parts. (1) — the course structure, which consists of the course name and a list of the projects and tasks. This example demonstrates the “Kotlin Onboarding: Introduction” course [2], which consists of nine projects. (2) — the progress bar for the current project. This example shows that the current project consists of nine tasks. (3) — the description of the current task in the Markdown format. (4) — static predefined hints provided by the task creator (e.g., some extra explanations or general ideas for solving the problem). Finally, (5) — the output of the testing system, which is available after pressing the “Check” button. This output shows if the current student solution passes the tests.

Figure 1.1: The user interface of the JetBrains Academy plugin for the “Kotlin Onboarding: Introduction” course: (1) course structure, (2) the progress bar for the current project, (3) task description, (4) hints provided by the course creator, (5) the output of the testing system.

2 GENERAL PIPELINE

2.1 GENERATING SUBGOALS

The final prompt for generating subgoals is presented in Figure 2.1.

```
Generate an ordered list of steps to solve the described coding task with each step marked as either "code" or "no-code" in the title. For example, "no-code" steps might involve actions like "End ... function", "Test ... function", "Read the task description and understand the requirements".

Each step is a detailed explanation of one distinct concrete action or operation that is understandable for beginners in Kotlin. Use built-in Kotlin functions in your solution. Do not write any example code blocks, except names of functions that can be used in the solution.

Be very detailed and precise, include at least 6 steps in the list, the more and clearer the better.

Here is information about the task, all blocks delimited with <>:

Task: <...>

Set of functions that might be implemented: <...>

Existing functions within the user's implementation can be used for the solution, without needing to describe their implementations: <...>

Hints: <...>

Theory: <...>

The solution can use only these strings: <...>
```

Figure 2.1: The prompt for generating subgoals.

2.2 GENERATING TEXTUAL AND CODE HINTS

The final prompt for generating the code hint is presented in Figure 2.2.

```
Generate a modified version of the provided student's code that incorporates the next step towards the solution based on the provided solution steps.

The modified code should not be a complete solution but should represent the next logical step that the student needs to take to solve the task.

Try to maintain the original structure of the student's code and focus especially on addressing common errors, while guiding the student towards the correct implementation.

Here is the list of steps that solves the task and the code, all delimited with <>:

The list of steps that solves the task: <...>

The student's code: <...>

<Error information if any>

Write the response in the following format:
Response: <non-code text>
Code: ```Kotlin
<code>
```

The code response should include the entire function or code block with the new changes incorporated into it.
```

Figure 2.2: The prompt for generating the code hint.

Table 2.1 presents the list of proposed heuristics to reduce the changes applicable to the student code.

Table 2.1: Heuristics to reduce the changes applicable to the student code.

| Heuristic                              | Description                                                                                                                                                       | Application Examples                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                             |
|----------------------------------------|-------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|----------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| Additive Statement Isolation           | If the first difference is an addition, only the statement is retained.                                                                                           | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li>• Function → Replace body with <i>TODO("Not yet implemented")</i></li> <li>• While, For → Remove body</li> <li>• If → Remove body and <i>else</i> block</li> <li>• When → Remove entries</li> <li>• Return → Proceed to simplify the expression following the return statement</li> </ul> |
| Intrinsic Structure Modification Focus | If the first difference is a modification that involves changes to the condition and the body of an expression, only the change related to the condition remains. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li>• Function → Change the function parameters</li> <li>• While → Change the condition</li> <li>• For → Change the loop range or the loop parameter</li> <li>• If → Change the condition or else block</li> <li>• When → Change the subject expression</li> </ul>                            |
| Internal Body Change Detection         | If there are several changes to the body of an expression, we only retain the first one.                                                                          | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <li>• Function, While, For, If, When, Return → Change the first difference in its body</li> </ul>                                                                                                                                                                                             |

The final prompt for generating the textual hint is presented in Figure 2.3.

```
Based on the given code and the improved version of the code, provide a concise textual hint that directly guides to improve the given code. Here is the current code and the improved version of the code, all delimited with <>:

The code:: <...>

The improved version of the code: <...>

Respond with a brief textual instruction in imperative form of what modifications need to be made to the code to achieve the improvements exhibited in the improved code. Do not write any code, except names of functions or string literals. Avoid explaining why the modifications are needed.
```

Figure 2.3: The prompt for generating the textual hint.

## 3 INTERNAL VALIDATION

### 3.1 “KOTLIN ONBOARDING: INTRODUCTION” COURSE

The “Kotlin Onboarding: Introduction” course [2] that we used for the validation consists of six console *projects*, the full overview of which can be found in the Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: “Kotlin Onboarding: Introduction” course projects.

| <b>Name</b>                 | <b>Description</b>                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                               |
|-----------------------------|------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| Story twister               | The goal of this game is to ask the user several fake questions, remember the answers, and then reveal the real questions to build a fun story from these answers.                                                                                                                                                                                                                                               |
| Chat                        | The purpose of this game is to ask questions to the user to get to know them better.                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                             |
| Bulls and cows (Mastermind) | This is a popular children’s game of guessing the hidden word. The main goal of the game is to guess the hidden word. With each attempt, the player receives the number of exact matches (correct letters in the right position) and partial matches (correct letters in the wrong position). For example, with ACEB as the hidden word, the BCDF guess will result in 1 full match (C) and 1 partial match (B). |
| Hangman                     | The purpose of this game is to guess the word chosen by the computer.                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                            |
| Console photoshop           | The goal of this project is to create a simple Photoshop console app that can apply different filters to character images.                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                       |
| Patterns generator          | The purpose of this project is to create an application for automatically generating character images of a given size and pattern.                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                                               |

### 3.2 VALIDATING THE GENERATION OF SUBGOALS

Table 3.2 describes all the proposed validation criteria for subgoals. Figure 3.1 illustrates example problems in the generated subgoals.

Table 3.2: Validation criteria for subgoals. The column "Example answer" includes the decisions for criteria for subgoals from Figure 3.1

| Criterion              | Definition                                        | Example answer                                                         |
|------------------------|---------------------------------------------------|------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| Amount                 | The number of the subgoals                        | 6                                                                      |
| Specifics              | Are the subgoals related to the specific actions? | No, subgoal 6 is not specific                                          |
| Independence           | Are the subgoals independent?                     | Yes                                                                    |
| Coding-specific        | Are the subgoals related to coding tasks?         | No, subgoal 6 is not coding-specific, it suggests testing the solution |
| Direction              | Do the subgoals lead towards solving the problem? | Yes                                                                    |
| Misleading information | Do the subgoals contain misleading information?   | No                                                                     |
| Granularity            | Are the subgoals limited to one step?             | No, subgoal 5 can be included into subgoals 2 and 3                    |
| Idiomatic              | Are the subgoals idiomatically correct?           | No, do not use suitable Kotlin built-ins (isLetter, filter, isEmpty)   |

```

Steps to solve the coding task:
1. Define the function isCorrectInput with the following signature:
 • Parameters: userInput (String), wordLength (Int), alphabet (String)
 • Return type: Boolean
2. Inside the isCorrectInput function, check if the length of the userInput is equal to the wordLength. If not,
inform the user that the length of their guess is incorrect by printing the following message:
 • "The length of your guess should be <wordLength> characters! Try again!"
 • Replace <wordLength> with the value of the wordLength parameter
3. Next, check if all symbols in the userInput are part of the alphabet. To do this, compare each character in
the userInput with the characters in the alphabet. If any character in the userInput is not found in the
alphabet, inform the user that their guess contains wrong symbols by printing the following message:
 • "All symbols in your guess should be the <alphabet> alphabet characters! Try again!"
 • Replace <alphabet> with the value of the alphabet parameter
4. If the length of the userInput is correct and all symbols are part of the alphabet, return true to indicate
that the input is correct.
5. If either the length of the userInput is incorrect or it contains wrong symbols, return false to indicate
that the input is incorrect.
6. Test the isCorrectInput function with different inputs to verify its correctness.

```

Figure 3.1: Example problems in the generated subgoals: 1) Limited recognition of built-in Kotlin functions, 2) Insufficient or excessive granularity, 3) Suggestion of redundant actions.

### 3.3 VALIDATING THE GENERATION OF HINTS

Table 3.3 describes all the proposed validation criteria for textual and code hints.

Table 3.3: Validation criteria for textual and code hints. The first eight criteria are taken from the work of Roest et al. [3], the last four in bold are proposed in this work.

| <b>Criterion</b>          | <b>Definition</b>                                                                           | <b>Example answer</b>                                                                                                                    |
|---------------------------|---------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------------|
| Feedback type             | What type of feedback does the generated hint represent?                                    | KTC-TR, KC-EXA, KH-TPS-TPSH                                                                                                              |
| Information               | Does the hint contain additional information, such as an explanation, tip or compliment?    | Yes, the hint provides an explanation on how to modify the 'getHiddenSecret' function and how to implement the 'isCorrectInput' function |
| Level-of-detail           | Is the hint a bottom-out hint (BOH) or a high-level description (HLD)?                      | BOH                                                                                                                                      |
| Personalized              | Does the hint refer to the student's code or approach?                                      | Yes                                                                                                                                      |
| Appropriate               | Is the hint a suitable next step, given the current state of the student program?           | Yes                                                                                                                                      |
| Specific                  | Is the hint limited to only one next step?                                                  | No, 2 steps                                                                                                                              |
| Misleading information    | Does the hint contain misleading information?                                               | Yes, modifies the 'getHiddenSecret' function, which cannot be modified in the current step                                               |
| Length                    | What is the length of the hint?                                                             | The text hint consists of 2 sentences and 57 words, the code hint consists of 16 new, 1 changed, 0 deleted code lines                    |
| <b>Intersection</b>       | Is the next step not already implemented in the student's code?                             | Yes                                                                                                                                      |
| <b>Code quality</b>       | Is generated code valid?                                                                    | Yes                                                                                                                                      |
| <b>Idiomatic</b>          | Is generated code written in the correct idiomatic way from the standpoint of the language? | No, can use the 'isLetter' function                                                                                                      |
| <b>Subgoals relevance</b> | Does the hint follow the list of subgoals?                                                  | No, implements all the subgoals at once                                                                                                  |

## REFERENCES

- [1] JetBrains Academy Plugin. <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/10081-jetbrains-academy>, 2024. [Online; accessed 27-June-2024].
- [2] Kotlin Onboarding: Introduction. <https://plugins.jetbrains.com/plugin/21067-kotlin-onboarding-introduction>, 2024. [Online; accessed 27-June-2024].
- [3] L. Roest, H. Keuning, and J. Jeuring. Next-step hint generation for introductory programming using large language models. In *Proceedings of the 26th Australasian Computing Education Conference*, pages 144–153, 2024.